

METHODOLOGY OF FORMING CRITICAL THINKING IN YOUTH STUDENTS DURING THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

Xurramova Sanobar Mahmadmurot qizi
Teacher of Termiz State Pedagogical Institute
E-mail: xurramova_sanobar@mail.ru
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Abstract: As an important component of society's social life, it is necessary to improve the education system and serve the interests of a fundamentally renewed society. Because education is the basis of society's development. Critical thinking of students and changing their attitude towards their work is very important in forming the ability of independent creative thinking in students.

Key words: students, consortium, time, critical thinking, critical analysis.

In Uzbekistan, reforms aimed at fundamental reform of the education system, raising the quality and content of education to a new level, creating a modern mechanism for training qualified personnel, and updating educational programs and literature are being implemented gradually and systematically.

Currently, in the development of our country, students in our educational institutions, which embody the content of Eastern education, should be taught independent critical thinking, as noted by the great thinkers of the Middle Ages, Khorezmi, Farabi, and Ibn Sina, and in the process of this critical thinking, In today's globalization process, it is important to show that acquired knowledge has a great advantage compared to knowledge obtained from a certain source.

In particular, this knowledge, developed more fully and quickly, becomes the students' beliefs and is considered a tool for their thinking and active practical critical thinking. Many modern scientists, pedagogues, psychologists and methodologists are engaged in researching the issues of critical thinking. In particular, in the works of V.V.Davidov, M.G.Davletshin, I.Y.Lerner, A.M.Matyushkin, M.I.Mahmutov, S.Rajabov, D.Shodiyev, E.Gaziyev, A.M.Umronkhojayev, the types of generalizations in the principles of problem-based education and their structure, organization of the educational process the structure of critical thinking, the specific features of individual components that determine ways of forming generalized methods of mental activity are analyzed.

At this point, the following words of President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev come to mind: "Critical analysis, strict discipline and personal responsibility should be the daily rules of every leader's activity".[1] As the head of our state said, if we teach critical analysis to our growing students from a young age, we think that these students will become mature cadres of our country in the future.

Creative sources of critical thinking go back to ancient times. In the natural and scientific works of medieval thinkers who lived in the Near and Middle East, we can see that there is a serious interest in various aspects of science, its principles, structure, criteria, and the connection of science with human intellectual development and education. The characteristic feature of the epistemological views of Khorezmi, Farabi, Beruni, Ibn Sina,

their comrades and followers is that the process of abstracting the image of an object in the human mind always attracted their attention, as a result of which the concept of the essence and uniqueness of this object was developed. developed and formed.

In learning the critical thinking of students, modern didactics uses the achievements of educational psychology, which deals with mental critical thinking of students in the process of reading.

The methods that serve to develop critical thinking among students in the educational system have been developed within the framework of the "Reading and Writing for Critical Thinking" project implemented by the "For Democratic Education" consortium.

developed, and in the development of active methods of critical thinking, they proceed from the following principles: What is critical thinking?

Thinking is a process similar to reading, writing, speaking and listening. It is an active, co-ordinating process that includes thoughts about a reality. Thinking is not a skill that can be developed out of context. Critical thinking is not a phenomenon that should be studied in an educational program or in a situation far removed from the general context of everyday life.

Brown (1989) argues that learning skills isolated from task and real-life goals may enable learners to perform well on objective tests, but they may not be able to apply those skills to new situations.[2]

The definition of learning and thinking according to Richer's definition is based on the results of research in the field of cognitive psychology, philosophy and multimedia culture education.[3]

Critical thinking and learning can only happen when educators understand and appreciate the diversity of ideas and experiences. Critical thinking does not occur in a "one-size-fits-all" mentality.

Developing critical thinking is not an easy task. It is not a task that is completed and forgotten at a certain age. At the same time, there is no perfect path to critical thinking. But there is a set of specific learning conditions that help to form critical thinkers. For him:

- to give time and opportunity to acquire the experience of critical thinking;
- giving students and young people an opportunity to think;
- acceptance of different ideas and thoughts;
- to ensure the activity of students in the educational process;
- it is necessary to convince students not to laugh;
- instill a sense of confidence in the ability of every student-young person to think critically;
- it is necessary to appreciate the occurrence of critical thinking. In this regard, students:
 - gaining self-confidence and understanding the value of one's own thoughts and ideas;
 - active participation in the educational process;
 - listening carefully to different opinions;
 - he should be ready to form his judgments and to return from them.

Time. Critical thinking takes time. Pearson, Hansen, and Gordon (1979) note that the creation of one's own fiction leads to an archaeological exploration of previous ideas, imaginations, encounters, and experiences.[4]

That's why:

- express their thoughts in their own words;
- exchange of critical opinions;
- able to express one's own ideas and receive answers to constructive suggestions;
- to be able to realize thoughts in the form of certain ideas, in a comfortable environment, and to be able to express one's ideas fully and clearly.

In order to have freedom in critical thinking, students should be allowed to say good and bad things, think about them, and create. Pupils and young people, after realizing the permissible situations, actively start critical analysis. Allowing for critical analysis is based on the principle of mindfulness. It is necessary to clarify the difference between analysis and exaggeration. Critical thinking is allowed in a friendly and productive environment that truly aims for thinking.

Diversity. Different thoughts and ideas appear in the thinking process of students. Varied thoughts and ideas arise only when the illusion that there is a single answer is eliminated. When the expression of ideas is limited, the students' thinking is limited. If there is only one answer, it is permissible to use various tools and processes so that students can find this answer.

Activity. Critical thinking is directly connected with the activity of students. Usually, students are passive listeners, because they believe that the teacher is knowledgeable or that the text reflects his knowledge, and because of this, the teacher is responsible for their knowledge. Active participation of students in the educational process and willingness to take responsibility for their studies gives expected results in critical thinking. Pedagogical approach of encouraging students to think, to share their ideas and opinions increases their activity. Mikhail Chikjentykh (1975) states that if students actively participate in the learning process at that complex level, they will greatly benefit from their participation in the learning process and feel a deep sense of satisfaction.[5]

Risk taking. Free-thinking is based on risk-taking. It is permissible to encourage people who fearlessly take risks in their educational activities. In the process of thinking, there may be cases where "stupid ideas" are unstructured combinations and concepts put forward. The teacher should explain this to students as a natural state of the educational process.[6] It is necessary to make sure that students should think in an environment that is free of risk, that is, where ideas are valued, where it is possible to highly motivate the active participation of students in thinking activities. *Qadrlash*. Tanqidiy fikrlashning omillaridan biri o`quvchi-yoshlarning fikrlash jarayonini qadrlashidir. Tashkil etilgan fikrlash jarayonida o`quvchi-yoshlar o`z g`oyalari, tasavvurlarining o`qituvchi tomonidan qadrlanayotganini tushungan holda chuqur mas`uliyat va e`tiborga yarasha javob qaytaradilar. O`quvchi-yoshlar o`z fikrlash jarayonini qadrlashni namoyish qilishga harakat qiladilar, unga va uning oqibatlariga nisbatan jiddiy munosabatda bo`la boshlaydilar.

- *Value*. During the organization of the thinking process, it is necessary to instill in the minds of students that their opinions and the results of their critical analysis are valuable. When the teacher requires students to simply process certain material, he should be free from ready-made templates and templates. This leads to the conviction that the mechanical reworking of other people's ideas is the most important and valuable. In fact, it is necessary to be able to show students and young people that their opinions, ideas and imaginations related to them are valuable. It is necessary for students and young people to be sure that their opinions are

valuable. They need to recognize that their opinion is very important and a significant contribution to the process of understanding and discussing the issue.

- *Mutual exchange of ideas. The process of thinking involves mutual exchange of ideas between students and young people. Mutual exchange of ideas between students and young people lays the foundation for their friendship in learning from each other. As thinkers, students are required to reveal to others their capacity for big ideas and simple mistakes. When receiving mutual opinions, students are required to listen carefully, to refrain from imposing their own views on the speaker and correcting other speakers. In response, students will have the opportunity to use the general thoughts of others. As a result of a wide-ranging discussion, the ability of students to analyze and identify their own ideas increases and integrate them into the system of ideas created in their knowledge and life experience. There are several models for organizing the thinking process. They are:*

- *self-confidence;*
- *active participation in work;*
- *exchange ideas with friends and teacher;*
- *being able to listen to others' opinions. [7]*

In conclusion, it is worth noting that the use of methods of gathering information, thinking and thinking provides an opportunity to solve the following important tasks:

- helps students to understand their goals;
- ensures activity in training;
- encourages effective discussion;
- helps students to formulate questions themselves and to be able to ask them in the form of questions;
- helps students express their personal knowledge;
- supports personal reading motivation of students;
- creates a mood of respect for any opinions;
- helps students develop their feelings for the characters;
- creates conditions for students' thinking that is valued;

The conclusion is that it is most important to have the ability to focus and motivate one's critical thinking, the ability to actively manage one's desires, and to value time in order to use every minute to improve one's personality.

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